

PROJECT NUMBER: 101018756

ACRONYM: GTCLC-NEG

PROJECT TITLE: Development of an innovative Gas Turbine Chemical Looping Combustor for Carbon Negative Power Generation

DELIVERABLE TITLE: 0D model

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: d3.2

Lead Beneficiary: CSIC

Work Package: WP1

Dissemination level: Public

Type: Report

Due date: 30 November 2022

Submission date: 30 November 2022

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INDEX

SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION	3
SECTION 2: THEORETICAL METHOD	7
SECTION 3: DESIGN OF THE FUEL REACTOR	8
SECTION 4: ENERGY ANALYSIS	15
SECTION 5: CONCLUSIONS	21
BIBLIOGRAPHY	22

SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION

Greenhouse gases released into the atmosphere through human activity are considered the biggest contributor to climate change. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the most prevalent greenhouse gas as it makes up 75 % of human emitted greenhouse gases and can last 300 years in the atmosphere [1]. CO₂ Capture and Storage (CCS) is an attractive option to reduce the emissions of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. CCS aims to harness a concentrated stream of CO₂ and store it underground, away from the atmosphere for a long period of time. Chemical looping combustion (CLC) is among new and developing CCS technologies. CLC is a technology for the conversion of fuels with inherent separation of CO₂ and efficient use of energy. Compared to traditional technologies, direct contact between fuel and air is avoided in CLC, as the oxygen required for the combustion is provided by an oxygen carrier, typically a metal oxide, which loops between two reactors known as air reactor and fuel reactor, and thus pure CO₂ can be obtained with reduced need for costly gas separation [2]. The metal oxide is oxidized in the air reactor and sent to the fuel reactor to combust the fuel and become reduced. The reduced metal oxide is sent back into the air reactor to start a new cycle. The oxygen carrier can be a manufactured material, an ore, or a waste. In the first case, the synthetic oxygen carrier is generally composed of a metal oxide based on nickel, copper, iron, manganese or a combined oxide of these metals together with a material that acts as support. Regarding ores and wastes, the most used material is ilmenite, followed by iron ores/wastes and manganese ores [3]. The majority of the CLC plants existing worldwide at the moment use the configuration composed of two interconnected fluidized-bed reactors operating at atmospheric pressure [4].

Specifically, until 2019, 43 of the 46 chemical looping units in operation at that time operated at atmospheric pressure. The three experimental pressurized installations totalled only 394 h of continuous operation, which represented approximately 4 % of the total time [3]. However, the study and demonstration of chemical looping technologies at pressurized conditions is a cornerstone for the development of these energy generation technologies with CO₂ capture, since the fact of operating under pressure can provide a series of very significant advantages: 1)

greater energy efficiency of the global process through the use of combined cycles for the production of electricity; 2) recovery of the latent heat of condensation in the outlet stream of the fuel reactor since a high pressure combustion process increases the condensation temperature; 3) lower electrical consumption associated with the compression stage of the highly-concentrated CO₂ stream obtained at the outlet of the fuel reactor; 4) increase in heat transfer coefficients that allows reducing the size and cost of heat transfer equipment in the chemical looping system; and 5) improved oxygen fuel conversion in the fuel reactor.

On the contrary, it should be taken into account that operating at pressurized conditions may entail some disadvantages such as a higher technical complexity of the design, construction and operation of the CLC unit. In particular, the operation stability of two interconnected pressurized fluidized bed to prevent the gas exchange between them (fuel and air reactors) may be challenging. Note that the circulating fluidized bed reactor (CFB) configuration is currently the most common option to design and operate chemical looping pilot plants. In this regard, the operation at pressurized conditions of experimental facilities based on this type of configuration poses a series of important techno-economic challenges [5]: 1) use of separate pressure shells for the main equipment that are part of the experimental unit (air reactor, fuel reactor, cyclones, loop seals, solid transport lines, etc.) in order to guarantee their mechanical integrity; 2) increased risk of operational problems in terms of solids fluidization malfunction and gas leakage between reactors due to pressure imbalance; 3) higher energy penalty due to the greater steam consumption required to fluidize the loop seal reactors at pressurized conditions. These challenges have encouraged research efforts based on other configurations to develop pressurized chemical looping technologies. These configurations are the following: moving bed reactor [6], [7], single fluidized-bed reactor or gas switching concept [8], [9], [10], internally circulating fluidized-bed reactor (ICR) [11], [12], fixed-bed reactor [13], [14], [15], and rotary bed reactor [16], [17], [18]. Each of these six configurations possesses its advantages and disadvantages having reached a different stage of development so far [19].

On the one hand, a CLC plant design based on the dual circulating fluidized bed reactor (DCFB) configuration initially proposed by Proll et al. [20] to operate at atmospheric pressure was evaluated. This unit consists of a fast fluidized air reactor and a turbulent fluidized fuel reactor. Under pressurized conditions, the fluidization regimes of both reactors are maintained and the basic dimensions of the DCFB reactor setup barely change with respect to the configuration proposed at atmospheric pressure [21]. This configuration, despite its complex technological challenges, is receiving the greatest research efforts and proof of this is that a 50 kW_{th} pressurized chemical looping combustion (PCLC) unit is under development at University of Kentucky [22] and the Korea Institute of Energy Research [23] has successfully put into operation the world's largest (0.5 MW_{th}) pressurized chemical looping system.

On the other hand, the ICR configuration was analysed, which incorporates most of the operational capabilities of the DCFB configuration, but simplifies the solids circulation mechanism in the system and the operation at high pressure conditions. Specifically, the ICR concept consists of a single vessel unit composed of two chambers, where the reduction and oxidation reactions take place, connected by two simple ports and a freeboard, which allows eliminating the loop seal reactors and the cyclones required in the DCFB configuration [5]. In an ICR system, both reactors operate in a bubbling fluidized bed regime and the circulation of the oxygen carrier inside the unit is achieved by means of a higher gas velocity in the air reactor than in the fuel reactor [19]. The main disadvantage of the ICR concept compared to the DCFB configuration lies in an increased risk of gas leakage between the two reaction chambers through the connection ports, which decreases the CO₂ capture efficiency and, consequently, the CO₂ concentration in the gas stream obtained at the outlet of the fuel reactor. This technology has recently been successfully demonstrated by the Norwegian University of Science and Technology and SINTEF Industry in a 4 kW PCLC unit (up to 0.6 MPa) with a Ni-based oxygen carrier using CO as fuel [5]. Besides, researchers from CanmetENERGY-Ottawa and Hatch Ltd. are currently collaborating on the design and construction of a 0.6 MW_{th} Pressurized Chemical Looping (PCL) reactor system based on this technology [24], [25].

The selection of the oxygen carrier to be used in pressurized CLC is a key issue for the development of this technology. Ilmenite was proposed as promising low-cost oxygen carrier to be used in CLC [26] and it has been widely used for the combustion of gaseous, liquid and solid fuels [27]. At atmospheric pressure, ilmenite presents poor results for methane combustion [28]. It would be expected that an increase of the reacting pressure may improve the CH₄ conversion due to the increase in the reaction rate [29]. This hypothesis should be confirmed in a CLC unit. Unfortunately, very low operational experience may be found regarding pressurized CLC. Then, modelling and simulation is a powerful tool to predict what may be expected.

This work intends to evaluate whether an increase in the operating pressure may improve the behavior of this material, taking into account the ilmenite kinetic parameters together with the fluid dynamics of the system. In addition, the evaluation of pressurized CLC for the energy use of natural gas is herein proposed considering the dual circulating fluidized bed reactor (DCFB) configuration and internally circulating fluidized bed reactor (ICR), in which the fuel reactor would be a fluidized bed reactor in the turbulent or bubbling regime, respectively.

Then, the general objective of this work was to ascertain future strategies for the development of the PCLC process based on DCFB and ICR configurations for natural gas combustion using ilmenite ore as oxygen carrier. Fluid dynamics considerations and theoretical predictions of methane combustion were evaluated to determine suitable design parameters at pressurized conditions. Results were discussed considering the scale-up potential of the PCLC configurations, identifying operating limits for the parameters/characteristics of a PCLC unit. In addition, the following specific objectives have been defined in this work:

- To analyze whether ilmenite ore is a suitable oxygen carrier to burn natural gas in a PCLC unit. In this regard, the poor reactivity exhibited by ilmenite to combust methane at atmospheric pressure discourages the use of this material in CLC processes with natural gas. However, recent studies [29], [30], [31] have shown that pressure could have a positive effect on the reactivity of this oxygen carrier during the methane reduction and air oxidation steps.

- To evaluate which configuration, i.e., DFBC or ICR, is more convenient in terms of a series of relevant design parameters for a PCLC unit such as combustion efficiency, reactor sizing and reactor pressure drop.
- To study whether the use of ilmenite as an oxygen carrier allows an optimal energy integration of the PCLC system. At this point, it should be highlighted that most of the techno-economic analyses on PCLC technology carried out to date are oriented towards power production in combined cycles [32], [33], [34], [35]. In order to achieve high net electric efficiency values, it is necessary to operate at high pressures (~ 2 MPa) and temperatures (>1200 °C) [21]. In this regard, these high temperatures represent a very ambitious research and technological challenge since the oxygen carrier must maintain adequate physicochemical properties at these conditions and this requirement has not been demonstrated yet with any oxygen carrier in continuous CLC pilot plants during long-term experimental campaigns. However, PCLC technology can be also implemented in other applications, such as heat production [36], [37], in which such high temperatures are not required and the projects can also become profitable from an economic point of view [37], [38]. Specifically, in this work an energy analysis of a CLC system, designed under DFBC and ICR configurations at atmospheric and pressurized (0.5 MPa) conditions, has been carried out for two different applications of heat generation: production of domestic hot water (DHW) and process steam.

SECTION 2: Theoretical Method

The fuel reactor was considered to operate in bubbling or turbulent regime depending on the reactor configuration selected, i.e., ICR or DFBC, respectively. A theoretical model previously validated at atmospheric pressure by Abad et al. [39], [40] was modified to consider fluid dynamics and reaction kinetics at pressurized conditions. The theoretical model for the fuel reactor considered the main processes affecting the reaction of methane with the oxygen carrier, such as reactor fluid dynamics, the reactivity of the oxygen carrier and the reaction mechanism. A description of the model can be found in Abad et al. [41]. The kinetic model was taken

from Tan et al. [30], which includes a term with a negative impact of the total pressure on the kinetic constant. Thus, kinetic constant will increase by 34 % instead of the expected increase of 70 % in absence of the negative impact of the term related with the total pressure. In addition, when an additional term related with the effect of the CO₂ partial pressure is considered, this increase is only 3 %. The low increase of the kinetic constant value with the total pressure will have a relevant impact on the combustion efficiency achieved and the CLC design.

SECTION 3: Design of the fuel reactor

A fluid dynamic study was done based on generalized map of gas/solid contacting presented by Kunii and Levenspiel [42] and Zerobin et al. [21]. Fig. 1 shows the map of fluidizing regimes for several total pressure values, ranging from 0.1 to 1.5 MPa, as a function of the gas velocity and particle size for ilmenite particles with density 3900 kg/m³.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Re}_{\text{mf}} &= \sqrt{27.2^2 + 0.0408Ar} - 27.2 \\ \text{Re}_t &= Ar^{1/3} \left[\frac{18}{Ar^{2/3}} + \frac{2.335 - 1.744\phi_s}{Ar^{1/6}} \right]^{-1} \\ \text{Re}_c &= 0.74Ar^{0.426} \\ \text{Re}_{\text{se}} &= 1.68Ar^{0.469} \end{aligned}$$

Fluidization in the bubbling regime is considered for gas velocities between u_{mf} and u_c . The transition boundaries for turbulent and fast fluidization regime are defined by u_c and u_{se} , respectively. The gas velocity for the transition between the bubbling, turbulent and fast fluidization decreases as the total pressure increases. In addition, these boundaries are different for the gas at the reactor inlet, mainly CH₄, or the gas at the reactor outlet, mainly CO₂ and H₂O. Note that the gas velocity increases as the methane is being converted in the fuel reactor, following the expansion given by the chemical reaction between methane and ilmenite:

Fig. 1. Fluidization regime in the flow map for the fuel reactor burning CH₄ with ilmenite particles. Continuous lines/symbols: reactor inlet conditions. Dashed lines/symbols: reactor outlet conditions. Selected conditions for bubbling regime (◆ ◆ ◆ ◆) or turbulent regime (■ ■ ■ ■). Closed symbols: gas velocity constant. Open symbols: cross section constant.

All these factors must be considered to define the operating conditions of the fuel reactor in both bubbling and turbulent/fast fluidization regime; see Fig. 1. Reference conditions at atmospheric pressure were properly selected to evaluate the effect of total pressure on the fuel reactor performance. Bigger particles of ilmenite were considered for the bubbling regime ($d_p = 0.25$ mm) compared to the turbulent regime ($d_p = 0.12$ mm). This fact was motivated by the improved gas conversion predicted by Abad et al. [39] for a larger particle size in the bubbling regime, while a higher development of the dilute region is predicted for the turbulent regime as the particle size decreases, which improves the gas conversion in agreement with results showed by Abad et al. [41]. Thus, the gas velocity at the reactor inlet was fixed at 0.32 m/s in the bubbling regime and 1.3 m/s in the turbulent regime. In the last case, the gas velocity was selected considering the existing design of a CLC unit at the Technological University of Vienna (TUV), which can be found in Pröll et al. [20]. In this way, the gas velocity is lower than u_c at the reactor inlet, but u_g becomes higher than u_c in the interphase between the bottom bed and the dilute region, i.e. when CH₄ was partially converted.

Fig. 2 shows the relation of the gas velocity with the cross section normalized per MW_{th} of thermal input. Thus, in order to have a higher gas velocity in the turbulent regime the cross section per MW_{th} should be decreased. The cross section for the bubbling and turbulent regime is 0.4 and 0.1 m²/MW_{th}, respectively. Here, two options have been considered for the design of the fuel reactor at pressurized conditions:

Fig. 2. Relation between design parameters (cross section and solids inventory, m_{FR}) and operating conditions (u_g , ΔP) for the design of the fuel reactor burning CH₄ at different total pressures.

First, the inlet gas velocity was maintained constant at the reference conditions for atmospheric pressure by decreasing the cross section of the reactor. The corresponding cross section for 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 MPa can be deduced from Fig. 2. In this case, the turbulent regime is maintained as the total pressure increases, or even a fast fluidization could be reached; see Fig. 1. In addition, the bubbling regime moves towards its upper region, or even turbulent regime can be found at total pressures

higher than 1.0 MPa. Interesting is the relation between the total pressure and the pressure drop showed in Fig. 2. Thus, if the cross section decreases with the total pressure, then the pressure drop should increase to maintain the same solids inventory.

Second, the cross section was maintained constant, which implies a decrease of the gas velocity with the total pressure; see Fig. 2. Considering the same solids inventory, the pressure drop would be maintained constant with the increase of P_t , being lower than those required for the first option described above. However, there is a risk of moving towards the bubbling region for the condition selected for the turbulent regime at atmospheric pressure; or even defluidization for the condition selected for the bubbling regime. Therefore, a limited evaluation of this option is done in this work.

Additional conditions varying the particle size or the gas velocity as a function of the total pressure could be selected, but a deeper evaluation of the effect of these parameters on the fluidization regime is out of the scope of this work.

The combustion efficiency of natural gas, η_c , was estimated with the theoretical model to evaluate the effect of the total pressure at several operating conditions.

$$\eta_c = \frac{\text{oxygen transferred to the fuel}}{\text{oxygen demanded for the fuel}} \quad (2)$$

First, it was simulated the effect of increasing pressure in a fuel reactor. Thus, Fig. 3 shows the evolution of the combustion efficiency in an existing fuel reactor when the power was proportionally increased with the pressure. This option should be considered to maintain the gas velocity constant when the total pressure was varied. Thus, the specific cross section (m^2/MW) decreased with P_t , as it was described in Fig. 2, but the amount of solids should increase to maintain the required specific solids inventory (here 500 kg/MW). As a consequence, the pressure drop (and also the bed height) was increased to values without practical interest (high height to section ratios).

Fig. 3. Effect of total pressure on the combustion efficiency at several fuel reactor temperatures when the cross section is decreased accordingly to the increase of the pressure drop. The relation between the cross section and the pressure drop is also shown. $m_{FR} = 500 \text{ kg/MW}_{th}$; $\phi = 2$.

Results are included in Fig. 3(a) for the bubbling regime and Fig. 3(b) for the turbulent regime. The solids circulation rate and solids inventory were fixed at 3.6 kg/s per MW_{th} , and 500 kg/ MW_{th} , respectively. This corresponds to an oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio of $\phi = 2$, as defined by Abad et al. [39]. Incomplete combustion was predicted at atmospheric pressure in agreement with results obtained by Pröll et al. [28] due to ilmenite is not a suitable oxygen carrier for the methane combustion. The potential of increasing the gas conversion by increasing the solids inventory or the solids circulation rate is limited, and it is not described in this work. The potential of increasing the fuel conversion by increasing the total pressure is analysed. In these cases, the pressure drop should be increased.

Both in the bubbling and turbulent regime the combustion efficiency increased with the reacting temperature due to an increase in the reaction kinetics. However, a relevant decrease in the combustion efficiency was predicted as the total pressure increased in the bubbling regime, even when the reaction rate increases with the total pressure. We conclude that the fluid dynamics variation with total pressure is highly relevant for the negative effect of pressure on the combustion efficiency. The gas conversion in the dense bed is limited due to the mass transfer between bubbles and emulsion phases, but the fraction of solids in the dense bed increases with the total pressure (e.g. from 57 % to 95 % at 0.1 and

1.0 MPa, respectively), which justifies the decrease of gas conversion with pressure. It is also relevant that the reaction rate does not increase as much as would be expected if the negative effect of the total pressure on the kinetics did not exist, as was determined by Tan et al. [30].

In general, the fuel conversion in the turbulent regime is higher than in the bubbling regime due to the development of the dilute region, which is more efficient converting the fuel gas than the dense bed. In the turbulent regime, the effect of the total pressure on the conversion efficiency shows the same decreasing trend with the total pressure at high temperature, i.e. 1000 and 1100 °C. Again, the main reason is the low efficiency of the dense bed burning the fuel. However, the opposite tendency was predicted at 800 °C, which is related to an improvement in the mass transference rate predicted in the upper part of the dense bed at pressurized conditions. This effect is evident when the dense bed is high and the reaction kinetics is low, i.e. high ΔP and 800 °C. In this case, an improvement of the fuel conversion was predicted with an increase of the total pressure.

From results in Fig. 3, it was deduced that the fuel conversion could be increased at high temperature. However, a safe temperature of 1000 °C would be recommended with ilmenite to avoid agglomerations problems. Therefore, this temperature was selected for the following simulations. In addition, it is not expected an improvement of the fuel conversion by increasing the total pressure when the cross section was correspondingly decreased to maintain the inlet gas velocity constant.

Finally, from the results shown in Fig. 3, it can be concluded that the pressure drop in the reactor increases considerably as the total pressure increases while maintaining a constant section, which implies the decrease of the specific cross section (m^2/MW). This leads to very high bed heights in the reactor, which would be an insurmountable challenge from a technical point of view.

In order to maintain the pressure drop constant, the specific cross section may be also maintained with pressure; i.e. the pressure to section ratio is not varied. This condition may be achieved either modifying the section of the reactor or maintaining the fuel flow and power constant with the pressure variation. In this case, the inlet gas velocity may decrease to

velocities below u_{mf} or u_c for the bubbling and turbulent conditions, respectively, as the pressure increases; see Fig. 1. However, an increase of the pressure up to 0.5 MPa makes possible the maintenance of the fluidization regime. Thus, considering the cross section selected for atmospheric pressure in the bubbling regime of $0.4 \text{ m}^2/\text{MW}$, the combustion efficiency was 73.6 %. With the same cross section, the inlet gas velocity was reduced by 5 at 0.5 MPa, but the combustion efficiency was increased to 76.7 %. This fact was related to the improvement of the mass transference in the dense bed with the decrease of the gas velocity.

To evaluate the relevance of the inlet gas velocity, some simulations were performed varying the cross section at 0.5 MPa, see Fig. 4. The combustion efficiency increased when the gas velocity was decreased. At the same time, the pressure drop also decreases to keep constant the solids inventory of $m_{FR} = 500 \text{ kg}/\text{MW}_{th}$. This effect was also predicted for the turbulent regime, but with a lower relevance. In fact, the combustion efficiency values predicted with $0.1 \text{ m}^2/\text{MW}_{th}$ at 0.1 and 0.5 MPa were 84.4 and 78.7 %, respectively. Here, the high decrease in the inlet gas velocity when the total pressure was increased caused a decrease of solids in the dilute region, which are highly active converting CH_4 [39], [41]. As a consequence, the gas conversion could not be increased with the total pressure.

Fig. 4. Effect of the inlet gas velocity on the combustion efficiency for the bubbling and turbulent regimes. The inlet gas velocity was varied changing the cross section of the fuel reactor, and its relation with the pressure drop is also shown. $P_t = 0.5 \text{ MPa}$, $T_{FR} = 1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $m_{FR} = 500 \text{ kg}/\text{MW}_{th}$, $\phi = 2$. Solid and dashed lines correspond to the values of combustion efficiency and cross section, respectively. Blue color is referred to bubbling regime and red color to turbulent regime.

A deeper evaluation of the effect of the particle size or gas velocity on the combustion efficiency is out of the scope of this work. However, the optimization of operating conditions considering these parameters and the flow map in Fig. 1 is encouraged for future works.

From the above simulations, the fuel conversion was relatively low, typically 60–80 % at 0.5 MPa and 1000 °C. Ilmenite is known to be an oxygen carrier with low reactivity towards CH₄, and both atmospheric and pressurized conditions were not suitable to achieve complete conversion of natural gas. A sensitivity analysis on the kinetic constant was done in order to estimate the required oxygen carrier reactivity to achieve 99 % combustion efficiency with $m_{FR} = 500 \text{ kg/MW}_{th}$. At 0.1 MPa, the kinetic constant should be multiplied by 6 and 4 in the bubbling (0.4 m²/MW_{th}) and turbulent regime (0.1 m²/MW_{th}), respectively. At 0.5 MPa, the multiplying factor should be 8 and 4.5.

Although the possible benefits of increasing the pressure on the fuel conversion has not been confirmed both in bubbling and turbulent regimes, some advantages may be still expected from an energy point of view. These possible benefits are evaluated in the next section.

SECTION 4: Energy analysis

This work has been completed with an energy analysis carried out with the Aspen HYSYS V12.1 process simulation software of a CLC plant for

the production of heat in the form of domestic hot water (DHW) or process steam in which the fuel reactor operates in a bubbling (ICR configuration) or turbulent (DFCB configuration) regime at atmospheric (0.1 MPa) or pressurized conditions (0.5 MPa) using ilmenite as oxygen carrier. Likewise, the presence of a turbo-expander for the production of electrical power from the hot gas stream obtained at the outlet of the air reactor has been analysed. In total, 6 different cases have been studied, see Table 1. In order to perform this analysis, the previously mentioned CH₄ combustion efficiency values have been considered. These results were obtained with the model developed by Abad et al. [39] when the temperature in the fuel reactor was 1000 °C, the inventory of ilmenite in this reactor was 500 kg/MW_{th}, and the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio, i.e., parameter ϕ , was 2. This model also provides other important parameters for the process, such as the operating temperature in the air reactor and the pressure drop in the fuel reactor. 1 MW of thermal power has been taken as a reference for all the cases analysed.

Table 1. Process simulation cases. Definitions and model outputs.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
FR regime	Bubbling	Bubbling	Turbulent	Turbulent	Bubbling	Turbulent
Pressure (MPa)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1
Turboexpander	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
T _{FR} (°C)				1000		
Input thermal power (MW _{th})				1		
CH₄ combustion efficiency (%)	76.7	76.7	78.7	78.7	73.6	84.4
Oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio, ϕ				2		
Solids inventory in the FR (kg/MW _{th})				500		
T _{AR} (°C)	1035	1035	1035	1035	1038	1041
Pressure drop FR, ΔP_{FR} (kPa)	12	12	48	48	12	48

Fig. 5 shows the process flow diagram of the CLC plant for one of the studied configurations, in particular, the one in which both reactors operate at pressurized conditions (0.5 MPa) and a turbo-expander is installed at the outlet of the air reactor (Case 1 or 3). In this CLC plant, the

methane and air streams fed to the fuel and air reactors are preheated in a series of heat exchangers (HX₁-HX₃) used to cool the pure CO₂ stream produced at the outlet of the fuel reactor after each compression stage. Once preheated, both currents are pressurized through their corresponding compressors. In Cases 5 and 6, evaluated at atmospheric pressure, the compressors are replaced by a blower, in the case of the methane stream, and by a fan, in the case of the air stream. An additional air stream is sent to an air separation unit (ASU) to produce the amount of pure oxygen required to burn in the O₂ polishing unit the methane that is not converted in the fuel reactor. This unit has a heat exchanger (HX₇) to recover the heat generated in the combustion of the unburned methane. Downstream of the O₂ polishing unit, two heat exchangers (HX₄-HX₅) are installed to use the energy content of the fuel reactor outlet stream, and a water recovery unit is next located to remove this compound and obtain a pure CO₂ stream. The CO₂ stream is then compressed by a series of compressors. These compressors operate with a pressure ratio between inlet and outlet of 5. In the pressurized cases, two compressors are installed in series, whereas a third compressor is included in Cases 5 and 6 at atmospheric pressure. In all cases, the final properties of the compressed CO₂ stream are 12.5 MPa and 35 °C. The gaseous stream coming out of the air reactor passes through a heat exchanger (HX₆) that recovers heat for the production of DHW or process steam. In Cases 1 and 3, where a turboexpander is considered, the inlet temperature at this piece of equipment is 732 °C. The outlet temperature and pressure of the turbo-expander are 439.8 °C and 0.1 MPa, respectively. In addition, at the outlet of the turbo-expander, another heat exchanger (HX₉) has been installed in order to maximize the heat recovery from the depleted air stream by cooling up to 150 °C. In cases where the turbo-expander is not included, the outlet temperature of the HX₆ unit is also 150 °C. Finally, Fig. 5 shows the heating process of the cold water stream ($T_{in} = 45$ °C, $P_{in} = 0.1$ MPa) through the heat exchangers to obtain the corresponding stream of DHW or process steam. In the case of the DHW stream, the final values of temperature and pressure are 90 °C and 0.1 MPa, respectively, whereas the process stream is produced at 350 °C and 4 MPa.

Fig. 5. Process flow diagram of the CLC unit. Cases 1 and 3.

Table 2 shows the results of the energy balance for the different cases studied in this analysis. The electric power is consumed to operate the ASU unit and to compress the CO₂ stream at the outlet of the fuel reactor as well as the methane and air streams fed to the fuel and air reactor, respectively. The main electrical consumption corresponds to the compression of the air stream fed into the air reactor when it operates at 0.5 MPa (Cases 1–4). This consumption decreases drastically in Cases 5 and 6 when the CLC plant operates at atmospheric pressure and the air compressor is replaced by an air fan. The second most important electrical consumption lies in the energy demand of the ASU cryogenic unit for the production of pure oxygen to burn the amount of methane that is not converted in the fuel reactor. Therefore, it is related to the CH₄ combustion efficiency values shown in Table 1. A consumption of 0.639 kW_eh/Nm³ O₂ has been estimated [36]. Finally, it should be pointed out that the power required to compress the pure CO₂ stream obtained at the outlet of the fuel reactor is higher in Cases 5 and 6 since it is necessary to install an additional compressor to increase the pressure from atmospheric pressure up to the final pressure of 12.5 MPa. These

GTCLC-NEG

electrical consumptions are partially compensated only in Cases 1 and 3 in which a turbo-expander is installed at the outlet of the air reactor.

Table 2. Energy balance of the CLC cases. Input power = 1 MW_{th} (as CH₄ fed into the FR).

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
Electric power						
W_{compCO2_1} (kW_e)	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.1	8.1
W_{compCO2_2} (kW_e)	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.6	8.6
W_{compCO2_3} (kW_e)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.3	10.3
W_{comp_CH4} (kW_e)	12.6	12.6	13.2	13.2	0.5	1.9
W_{comp_air} (kW_e)	89.0	89.0	89.0	89.0	5.0	20.1
W_{ASU} (kW_e)	29.9	29.9	27.4	27.4	33.9	20.0
Electric power input (kW_e)	147.7	147.7	145.8	145.8	66.3	68.9
W_{turboexpander} (kW_e)	98.9	0	98.9	0	0	0
Electric power output (kW_e)	98.9	0	98.9	0	0	0
Electric power balance (kW_e)	-48.8	-147.7	-46.9	-145.8	-66.3	-68.9
Thermal power						
HX₄ (kW_{th})	70.6	70.6	70.6	70.6	31.8	31.8
HX₅ (kW_{th})	109.1	109.1	109.1	109.1	108.9	108.9
HX₆ (kW_{th})	106.6	299.2	106.6	299.2	301.1	301.1
HX₇ (kW_{th})	214.1	214.1	196.0	196.0	242.8	143.3
HX₈ (kW_{th})	426.6	426.6	445.6	445.6	306.7	404.9
HX₉ (kW_{th})	93.6	0	93.6	0	0	0
Thermal power output (kW_{th})	1020.5	1119.5	1021.5	1120.4	991.3	990.0
Energy applications						
DHW mass flow (kg/h)	1044.0	1144.9	1045.0	1145.9	1014.0	1012.7
Steam mass flow (kg/h)	67.7	74.3	67.8	74.3	65.8	65.7
Total energy balance (kW)	971.7	971.8	974.6	974.7	925.1	921.2

The heat generated in the CLC plant comes from the outlet gas streams of the fuel (HX₄ and HX₅) and air (HX₆ and HX₉) reactors, the O₂ polishing

unit (HX₇), and the exothermic reactions that take place in the air reactor between air and the oxygen carrier (HX₈). Firstly, the heat exchanged in the HX₄ is higher for the cases at pressurized conditions than for the ones at atmospheric pressure, since the latent heat of condensation of the water generated in the fuel reactor can be used when the CLC unit operates under pressure. For all the cases, the outlet temperatures of the O₂ polishing unit, HX-5 and HX-4 are 1000 °C, 350 °C and 130 °C, respectively. Secondly, the heat exchanged in the HX-6 unit is lower in Cases 1 and 3, in which the turbo-expander is included, since the outlet temperature in this heat exchanger in these cases is higher (732 °C) than in the other cases (150 °C). Thirdly, the heat generated in the O₂ polishing unit (HX-7) depends on the methane conversion degree achieved in the CLC plant using ilmenite as oxygen carrier. In this regard, the higher the CH₄ combustion efficiency value, the lower the heat recovered in the O₂ polishing unit. The heat generated in the air reactor (HX-8) is higher at pressurized conditions and in all the cases it is the main energy source for the production of DHW or process steam. Finally, 93.6 kWth are recovered in Cases 1 and 3 from the heat exchanger (HX₉) located downstream of the turbo-expander. The highest amounts of thermal energy are produced in Cases 2 and 4. In both cases, the working pressure is 0.5 MPa and there is no generation of electrical power through a turbo-expander. On the contrary, the worst results in terms of thermal power output are obtained in Cases 5 and 6 at atmospheric pressure. In terms of DHW and process steam, the mass flow values vary between 1012.7 and 1145.9 kg H₂O/h and between 65.7 and 74.3 kg steam/h, respectively. From a global energy point of view, that is, taking into account the electric power balance, it can be concluded that the energy efficiency achieved in the pressurized cases (Cases 1–4) is slightly higher than that obtained in the cases performed atmospheric pressure, fundamentally because at pressurized conditions it is possible to take advantage of the latent heat of condensation of the water generated in the fuel reactor. In contrast, the fluidization regime of the fuel reactor, i.e., bubbling or turbulent, has a negligible effect on the energy analysis when the CLC unit operates at 0.5 MPa.

The results presented in this work intend to provide some guidelines to analyze the potential of PCLC technology for the production of heat from

natural gas with special emphasis on the configuration/design of the fuel reactor and the energy integration of the continuous PCLC unit. This study has been carried out considering an ilmenite ore as oxygen carrier, but it could be applied to any other material. To complete this analysis of PCLC technology, it is recommended to carry out a detailed economic study that includes capital expenditures (reactors, turbomachinery, heat exchangers, etc.), operating costs (natural gas, electricity, maintenance and operation, etc.) and income generated.

SECTION 5: Conclusions

Design parameters, such as the specific cross section area and solids inventory, should be carefully selected to operate with suitable operating conditions, e.g. gas velocity and pressure drop, in the PCLC of natural gas. Uncompleted combustion was predicted with ilmenite both at atmospheric pressure and pressurized conditions. An oxygen carrier with a higher reactivity would be required to achieve full combustion with low pressure drop values. The negative effect of total pressure on the reaction kinetics has a relevant influence on the low combustion efficiencies predicted. This behaviour should be studied and understood in order to design oxygen carriers with a reaction kinetic barely affected by the total pressure. Finally, from an energy point of view, it is beneficial to operate under pressurized conditions since in this case the latent heat of condensation of the water generated in the reduction reactor can be recovered. However, the fluidization regime of the fuel reactor, i.e., bubbling or turbulent, has little influence on the overall energy balance of a PCLC process when ilmenite is used as oxygen carrier. In addition to the results obtained in this work, a thorough assessment of technical risks and a techno-economic analysis would be required in order to make a final decision about the feasibility of operating at pressurized conditions in CLC systems.

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